

THEORETICAL BASICS OF PRIMARY PIANO PERFORMANCE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article contains opinions on collaborative performance on the piano. Also, the scientific-theoretical importance of piano performance in music culture is explained in detail.

Keywords: Music culture, piano, art, ensemble, concert, professional performance, musical instrument.

It is advisable to start learning the art of collaborative performance with lessons in the piano ensemble class. Unlike other forms of collaborative performance, a piano duet brings together performers of the same specialty. This facilitates mutual understanding between them. This genre has a long history. At one time, there were two types of piano duets on the concert stage: one piano duet and two piano duets. By the present time, the duet on two pianos has taken a firm place in practice: it is difficult to find performers who play four hands together on one piano, as in the time of Liszt and Rubinstein. Today, playing four hands on one piano can be found mainly in home music lessons and in the educational process. It is not for nothing that the piano duet is widespread in professional concert practice. The uniqueness of such an ensemble shows the complete freedom of the performers. In this too, a performer will have his own instrument. Due to the presence of two players and two performers, the rich possibilities of the piano expand even more. This feature attracted the attention of composers.

There is another form of piano ensemble - eight-hand performance on two pianos. This kind of "quartet" performance is very useful in children's music schools. Rather than duet performance in an ensemble, joining four performers will encourage the development of a sense of collective responsibility. Eight-handed performance was also used in conservatory classes. The performance program of piano ensembles can be divided into original works created specifically for the ensemble (as well as concert transcriptions) and works reworked to popularize symphonic music. For four-hand performance on one piano: European composers V. A. Mozart, F. Schubert, R. Schumann, K. Weber, M. Ravel, S. Rachmaninov, Uzbek composers R. Abdullaev, M. Otajonov, E. Salikhov, O. Abdullaeva, H. Hasanova and other major composers created special works. However, the concert program created for four-hand performance on two pianos is richer and more diverse. All types of piano ensemble and both sections

of the performance program (concert pieces and reworked "pianos") can be used equally successfully in the educational process. Reworked pianos of orchestral works are a good material for developing the skill of reading notes, quickly following the text of notes, playing the piece "in sketch".

Listening to a particular symphony in concert, on the radio, or on tape, and trying to play it independently are two different things. No matter how carefully you listen to the work, it is difficult to get as much information as playing and independent interpretation when studying it closely. In this, the performer not only experiences the learning process, but also feels aesthetic joy. String and percussion players are part of the orchestra and participate in the rebirth of symphonic works. Pianists are exempt from this. In many cases, pianists want to try playing pieces composed for orchestra. Playing symphonic music in four-hand form on the piano can satisfy this intention to some extent. Original duet works and concert transcriptions are intended for public performance and require perfect performance. Studying these works helps to understand the diverse requirements of the ensemble, enriches the creative thinking of the performers and perfects their skills. Let's start with the "alphabet" of collaborative performance. Let's see what skills of duet performance make up the content of this "alphabet". The following sections of elementary education can be defined as the first step in mastering the "ensemble technique":

- features of sitting and pedaling in a four-handed performance position on one piano;
- ways to achieve synchronicity in obtaining and solving the tone;
- equality of tone distributed among co-performers;
- coordination of sound production methods; peer-to-peer voice transmission;
- equality in the unity of several votes performed by different partners;

According to the level of complexity of artistic issues, the technical issues of collaborative performance also expand:

- overcome polyrhythmic difficulties;
- use of special timbre possibilities of piano duet;
- pedalization on two pianos, etc.

The difference between a four-hand performance on one piano and a solo performance begins with sitting in front of the grand piano, because each pianist has only half of the keyboard at his disposal. Partners need to be able to "share" the keyboard and, in particular, keep their elbows in such a way that they do not interfere with each other when approaching or intersecting vocal movements (one elbow under the other). Which of the partners should pedal during the

four-handed performance? In many cases, students do not know this. It should be noted that the pedalization is performed by the player of the Secondo (second) part, because the second part often serves as the harmonic foundation (bass) for the melody in the upper register. In this case, it is necessary for this performer to listen carefully to his partner and consider the musical fabric that will be heard in his party. While listening to one's own performance, at the same time listening to the partner, or rather, the general sound of both parties forming a single unit, is the basis of all types of ensembles.

Solo performance teaches the pianist to listen to himself, his attention is focused on a certain point and it is not easy to change it. It will not be enough for the student to say, "You are not listening to your partner." This situation leads to the ambiguity of the double point, he and that ("I" and "she"). When listening, you should listen not to yourself and him, but to the general sound of the ensemble. The inability to listen to the general sound is evident in the way the pianist sits: "staring" at the keyboard, carefully observing the movements of his fingers; his waist is extremely bent, and in melodic sections he turns his head to one side as if trying to hear the melody with one ear. In such a case, the sound of both parties remains on the same side, and it is impossible to have a good opinion about their own performance! It is very helpful to instruct the student playing the second part to pedal the first part instead of playing his own part. In this case, it is determined that this situation is unusual and the student's attention increases. Then the pianists should be replaced. Then the partner pianists will understand their shortcomings better. In many cases, the continuity of the four-hand performance is broken due to the fact that the pianists are unable to scroll through the notes and do not know how to count the long pauses. Depending on the degree of occupation of the hand, the students should decide whether it is more convenient for a certain performer to scroll through the note; In the absence of a "free hand" during the performance, it will be necessary to determine which part of the sheet music should be played by heart. It is not an easy task to quickly and nimbly flip a note with one hand at the right time and continue playing with the other; for this, it is necessary to learn by forming skills with the help of special exercises.

Pianists do not have the ability to count long pauses correctly like orchestra players. Therefore, it is necessary to explain to the students that the exact counting of pauses should be done during the first acquaintance with the sheet music, and this is not necessary later. When counting pauses, it is possible to expand the range of the count, and also to use certain phrases, imagining the

general movement and structure of the musical development. After a break, it works well to join in with a piece of music that is playing at a partner's party to overcome the fear of going right into the music. In this case, the pause is filled with a lively musical feeling, as opposed to a dull silent character.

It's the easiest thing to start performing together. However, getting two sounds in sync is not that easy, it takes a lot of practice and mutual understanding. It is necessary to explain to the students the technical terms of the conducting auftakt method and the use of this method by the pianist in a particular situation. When playing on one or two pianos in parallel, with the hands of the partner players facing each other, auftakt is a slight movement of the palm (high point is clearly defined), nodding of the head, or signaling with the eyes (pianists facing each other when located) can be done through It is also helpful to advise both players to breathe at the same time during the auftakt. This ensures that the performance starts naturally. In this case, the teacher may offer the musicians to try the piece several times with the help of the conductor's instructions, and then allow them to do it independently. It does not matter which performer gives the auftakt: each of the partners must be able to do it. Any ambiguity in the mismatch of sounds should be taken seriously.

At first glance, it is difficult to quickly achieve such unity, which is imagined as easy. It is important to note that in addition to synchronous execution, synchronous completion is also important. Chords that don't end properly can pollute the pause, distort it, and create a very unpleasant impression. It is also worth talking about the great expressive value of the pause. Not paying attention to pauses is especially common among young performers. The technical issue is not limited to synchronicity in the production of individual sounds. Partners must achieve equality of weight in performance. Such equality should be shown not only in the case of individual chords, but also in parallel voices (octave description of the melody in different parts). Performance in an ensemble requires full cooperation from the performers from the first beats. In this case, the performers will have to walk along a common path towards a common goal. Orderliness of performance in cooperation is a special field of work characteristic of ensemble classes. Technical difficulties are found not only in the musical fabric of each part, but also in the elemental coordination of the performance of the duet participants. Playing sheet music in two parts usually makes it easier to play (it's easier to play a part than the whole piece), but it can also be a challenge. Of course, music that one pianist can easily play with both hands is difficult for two players to play with two hands. Performers feel

uncomfortable in this. One of the other elementary technical methods of the ensemble is the hand-to-hand transfer of the passage, melody, accompaniment, etc. by the partners.

Pianists must learn to pick up an unfinished phrase and pass it on to their partner without disrupting the musical fabric. It is also possible to talk about the performance dynamics. A relatively common shortcoming of student performance is dynamic uniformity: the entire piece is played in *mf* and *f*. Piano dynamics can rarely be heard in the first practice of a four-hand ensemble! *Pianissimo* can't be said at all! It is necessary to explain to students that the dynamic range of four-handed performance is wider than that of solo performance. After all, the power of two pianists makes it possible to use the keyboard to the full, to compose more voluminous, dense, heavy chords. To achieve a bright dynamic effect, the power of two people needs to be equally distributed. Of course, this does not make the piano sound twice as loud. However, despite this, a certain result is achieved.

If the student is satisfied with the artistic task performed together for the first time, if he is happy with the general emotional excitement of the joint actions as a helper and expert, then it can be considered that the classroom training has given its important result. Although this performance is far from perfect, this should not discourage the teacher. After all, deficiencies can be eliminated in the next work process. In this case, we need to consider another factor as more valuable - the border between soloist and ensemble performer disappears, and the pianist understands the uniqueness and fun of collaborative performance.

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